

Effects of urban dust emissions on fine and coarse PM levels and composition

Stylios Kakavas^{a,b} and Spyros N. Pandis^{a,b,c,*}

^aInstitute of Chemical Engineering Sciences, Foundation for Research and Technology Hellas (FORTH),
26504, Patras, Greece

^bDepartment of Chemical Engineering, University of Patras, 26500, Patras, Greece

^cDepartment of Chemical Engineering, Carnegie Mellon University, Pittsburgh, PA 15213, USA

* Corresponding author, Department of Chemical Engineering, University of Patras, Patra GR-26500,
Greece, Tel: +30 2610 969510; fax: +30 2610 969713.

E-mail address: spyros@chemeng.upatras.gr (S. N. Pandis).

Abstract

Simulation of the concentration of urban dust and its interactions with other inorganic components of particulate matter (nitrate, ammonium, sulfate) remains a major modeling challenge. In this study the chemical transport model PMCAMx is applied over Europe during the EUCAARI 2008 summer campaign. The default emission inventory leads to significant underprediction of PM₁₀ levels in both urban and rural areas. We test the hypothesis that this is due to a large extent to an underprediction of urban dust by increasing the corresponding emissions by a factor of ten. This leads to improved PM₁₀ predictions in all sites in Europe and especially in urban areas. The PM₁₀ fractional bias of the model decreased by 23% and the fractional error by 13%. Average predicted PM₁ nitrate decreases on average by 20% over the modeling domain due to the increased urban dust. Fine nitrate reductions of 0.5-1 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ are predicted for areas of the Netherlands, Belgium, France and United Kingdom. Fine ammonium and sulfate also decrease by 9% and 7.5% respectively, when the higher urban dust emissions are used. At the same time predicted coarse nitrate concentrations increase on average by 10% with absolute increases of 1.2 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ in the Netherlands and Belgium and 1 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ in Paris. Coarse ammonium and sulfate increase by 16% and 6% respectively due to the higher levels of urban dust.

1. Introduction

Atmospheric particulate matter from anthropogenic and natural sources has adverse impacts on human health and contributes to climate change. Dust is a significant component of atmospheric coarse particulate matter (particles with diameter from 1 to 10 μm). Dust in urban areas is mainly emitted by transportation through re-

37 suspension (Amato et al., 2009, 2011; Karanasiou et al., 2011; Pant et al., 2013; Querol
38 et al., 2004; Viana et al., 2007; Athanasopoulou et al., 2010) and is often called road
39 dust. Road dust may dominate non-exhaust particulate matter emissions in urban areas
40 (Denier van der Gon et al., 2010; Denier van der Gon et al., 2013; Amato, 2018).
41 Exposure to high dust levels can have negative effects on human health including
42 increases in hospital admissions (Chang et al., 2011) and respiratory problems for
43 children (Neisi et al., 2017; Keet et al., 2018). Agricultural operations such as plowing,
44 disking, harrowing, and harvesting also emit significant amounts of dust in rural areas
45 (Winiwarter et al., 2009). Natural sources, such as wildfires, emit dust through
46 resuspension due to the intense turbulence that they generate (Wagner et al., 2018). It
47 is estimated that soil dust accounts for 10% of PM₁₀ emissions during early fire stages
48 (Kavouras et al., 2012). Dust transport from deserts such as the Sahara is another major
49 natural source (Laurent et al., 2008). In this study we will focus on periods during which
50 Europe is not affected by transport of dust from the Sahara.

51 Dust is mainly inert, but also includes small amounts of Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺, K⁺, etc.
52 (Silva et al., 2000). These are chemically active and can participate in heterogeneous
53 reactions, for example forming nitrate or sulfate salts after reactions with HNO₃ or
54 H₂SO₄ vapors (Karydis et al., 2010, 2011). These reactions can also affect indirectly
55 fine particulate matter by changing the fine nitrate and sulfate levels (Wang et al., 2012;
56 Karydis et al., 2011). Previous studies have shown that the simulation of these dust
57 effects with the proper emissions can considerably improve model predictions of
58 inorganic PM (Moya et al., 2002; Laskin et al., 2005; Hodzic et al., 2006; Fountoukis
59 et al., 2009; Karydis et al., 2010, 2011, 2016; Wang et al., 2012; Trump et al., 2015).
60 Trump et al. (2015) showed the importance of the interactions of coarse-mode cations
61 such as sodium from sea spray with nitric acid for the fine PM levels in coastal areas of
62 Europe.

63 Emission inventories for the EU member states include emissions by
64 automobile tire and brake wear and automobile road abrasion (Amato, 2018).
65 Resuspension of the deposited road dust by transportation is a reemission and is not
66 included in the reporting requirements of the EU member states (Amato, 2018). As a
67 result, road dust emissions are not included in most official European emission
68 inventories leading to a serious underestimation of urban dust. Patra et al. (2008) found
69 that coarse PM levels in Central London increase due to traffic by a factor of 1.5 to 13
70 due to resuspension of road dust. Athanasopoulou et al. (2010) parameterized the road

71 dust emissions for the city of Athens and estimated using the chemical transport model
72 CAMx that this source is responsible for 10-40% of the PM₁₀ over the city. Kauhaniemi
73 et al. (2011) proposed and evaluated a vehicular dust resuspension emission model in
74 combination with a street canyon dispersion model in Helsinki. Their predictions were
75 found to be sensitive among others to precipitation. Rzeszutek et al. (2019) reported
76 improvements in the predictions of a street canyon model, when road dust emissions
77 were considered.

78 In atmospheric chemical transport models (CTMs) the particulate and gas
79 phases are often assumed to be in equilibrium. This assumption may lead to errors since
80 the coarse particles usually need hours to reach equilibrium (Meng and Seinfeld, 1996;
81 Karydis et al., 2011). Dynamic models simulate explicitly the mass transfer between
82 the gas phase and each particle group, minimizing this error. The hybrid method
83 (Karydis et al., 2010) combines both of these approaches assuming bulk equilibrium
84 for the fine aerosol (diameter up to 1 μm) and simulating the mass transfer between the
85 coarse aerosol and the gas phase using a dynamic approach (Capaldo et al., 2000). This
86 method is more computationally efficient than fully dynamic approaches and more
87 accurate than models that assume thermodynamic equilibrium for particles of all sizes.

88 In this study we quantify the effect of urban dust emissions on PM₁₀ levels but
89 also on the concentrations of the major inorganic PM components (sulfate, nitrate and
90 ammonium) in the fine and coarse modes.

91

92 **2. Model description**

93 PMCAMx is a three-dimensional chemical transport model (CTM) and the
94 research version of the publicly available CAMx model (Environ, 2003). It simulates
95 horizontal and vertical advection, horizontal and vertical dispersion, dry and wet
96 deposition and gas, aqueous, and aerosol chemistry. The gas-phase chemical
97 mechanism used includes 211 reactions of 18 radicals and 56 gases and is based on a
98 modified SAPRC mechanism (Carter, 2000; Environ, 2003). Furthermore, aqueous-
99 phase chemistry (Fahey and Pandis, 2001), inorganic aerosol formation (Gaydos et al.,
100 2003; Koo et al., 2003) and secondary organic aerosol formation (Lane et al., 2008) are
101 simulated. The organic vapors are assumed to be in pseudo-equilibrium with the organic
102 PM phase based on the Volatility Basis Set (VBS) framework (Lane et al., 2008;
103 Murphy and Pandis, 2009). The aerosol size and composition distribution is described
104 using 10 size bins with diameters from 40 nm to 40 μm . The aerosol species simulated

105 are primary and secondary organics, elemental carbon, crustal species, sodium,
106 chloride, sulfate, nitrate, ammonium, and water.

107 The formation of inorganic aerosol in PMCAMx can be simulated either with
108 the bulk equilibrium approach or the hybrid approach. The bulk equilibrium approach
109 is based on the assumption that the bulk aerosol and gas phases are always in
110 equilibrium. The amount of each species transferred between the aerosol and gas phases
111 is determined by the thermodynamic equilibrium model ISORROPIA (Nenes et al.,
112 1998) which treats the thermodynamics of NH_4^+ - Na^+ - SO_4^{2-} - HSO_4^- - NO_3^- - Cl^- - H_2O
113 aerosol systems. In the hybrid approach fine particles (diameter less than 1 μm) are
114 simulated assuming bulk equilibrium, while for the coarse particles (diameter from 1 to
115 10 μm) the mass transfer between the gas and particle phases is simulated explicitly
116 (Capaldo et al., 2000) by using the MADM model of Pilinis et al. (2000) as extended
117 by Gaydos et al. (2003). The thermodynamic equilibrium model ISORROPIA-II
118 (Fountoukis and Nenes 2007), which treats the thermodynamics of Ca^{2+} - K^+ - Mg^{2+} - NH_4^+
119 - Na^+ - SO_4^{2-} - HSO_4^- - NO_3^- - Cl^- - H_2O aerosol systems, is used for the calculation of the
120 equilibrium vapor pressures of HNO_3 , NH_3 , HCl , and also the aerosol water
121 concentration in this case.

122

123 **3. Model application**

124 The simulation period is the EUCAARI summer intensive measurement period
125 during May 2008. The modeling domain is a region of $5400 \times 5832 \text{ km}^2$, including all
126 of Europe with $36 \times 36 \text{ km}$ grid resolution and 14 vertical layers with a total height of
127 6 km above ground level (Fig. 1). Dust PM_{10} concentrations at the boundaries of the
128 domain are considered constant with typical small values and invariant with height and
129 along each boundary. In the north and west boundaries PM_{10} dust concentrations are
130 assumed to be $0.3 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, while in the south and east equal to $1 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$. Inputs to the
131 model such as vertical diffusivity, horizontal wind components, pressure, temperature,
132 water vapor, clouds and rainfall are provided by the Weather Research and Forecasting
133 (WRF) meteorological model (Skamarock et al., 2008).

134 The emission inventory used for all PM components including dust is the
135 EUCAARI Pan European emission inventory (Kulmala et al., 2011), based on the
136 IIASA's GAINS inventory (Klimont et al., 2002; Kupiainen and Klimont, 2004). Dust
137 emissions were separated from those of other PM components and the distribution of
138 dust particles has been improved. The default dust emission inventory includes dust

139 emissions from agricultural operations, non-exhaust road transport and wildfires. Dust
140 is assumed to represent 23% of the total PM₁ emissions by agriculture (Trippetta et al.,
141 2016) and 3% of total PM₁ emissions by non-exhaust road transport (Amato et al.,
142 2009). The PM₁₋₁₀ fraction of dust emissions is calculated based on the dust size
143 distribution of Bessagnet et al. (2008). Agricultural dust emissions for Spain, Italy,
144 Greece, Romania and Czech Republic have been added in the corresponding
145 agricultural areas assuming a mean dust emission rate equal to 0.33 kg d⁻¹ km⁻². The
146 agricultural areas have been determined based on the spatial distribution of ammonia
147 emissions for these countries. Emissions by wildfires are taken from IS4FIRES (Sofiev
148 et al., 2009) and the size and composition distribution of PM₁₀ is based on Andreae and
149 Merlet (2001). The PM_{2.5-10} fraction accounts for about 25% of the emissions by
150 wildfires.

151 Resuspended road dust emissions by transportation have been added in the
152 inventory since they were not included the original (Amato, 2018). These emissions
153 were estimated, as a zeroth order approximation, to be ten times the non-exhaust road
154 transport emissions (Kupiainen and Pirjola, 2011; Patra et al., 2008; Amato, 2018) in
155 the original emission inventory. These dust emissions are implicitly accounting also for
156 other urban dust sources.

157 The spatial distribution of dust emissions for the improved emission inventory
158 is shown in Fig. 2. Table 1 shows a summary of the default (low) and improved (high)
159 dust emission rates for the major sources of dust. Calcium, magnesium, potassium, and
160 sodium are assumed to represent a constant fraction of mineral dust mass: 2.4% for
161 Ca²⁺, 1.5% for K⁺, 1.2% for Na⁺ and 0.9% for Mg²⁺, based on Sposito (1989) and
162 Karydis et al. (2016). Table 2 also includes a summary of the emissions of trace
163 elements.

164 Details of the rest of the aerosol and gas emissions are described in Fountoukis
165 et al. (2011). More details about the initial EUCAARI TNO emissions are available in
166 Visschedijk et al. (2007) and Kulmala et al. (2011).

167 Daily average measurements of PM₁₀ concentrations from 43 sites are used for
168 the evaluation of the PMCAMx predictions. The predicted PM₁₀ concentration is
169 calculated assuming that there is zero water in the measured PM₁₀ mass. The location
170 and the main characteristics of the stations are shown in Fig. 1 and Table S1
171 respectively. The fractional bias and fractional error of the model predictions are used
172 as the metrics for the model evaluation. Fine aerosol mode PMCAMx predictions have

173 been evaluated by Fountoukis et al. (2011; 2014). Morris et al. (2005), proposed four
174 model performance levels: “excellent” (fractional bias $\leq \pm 15\%$ and fractional error \leq
175 35%), “good” (fractional bias $\leq \pm 30\%$ and fractional error $\leq 50\%$), “average”
176 (fractional bias $\leq \pm 60\%$ and fractional error $\leq 75\%$), and “problematic” (fractional
177 bias $\geq \pm 60\%$ and fractional error $\geq 75\%$).

178

179 **4. Model predictions and evaluation**

180 Predicted average ground-level PM₁₀ dust concentrations using the default dust
181 emissions are generally low, with average concentrations varying from 0.5 to 1 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$
182 over most of Europe except in the Netherlands and Belgium where the concentrations
183 exceed 4 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ due to high agricultural emissions (Fig 3a). PM₁₀ concentrations are
184 high over the Mediterranean Sea and over parts of the Atlantic due to high sea-salt
185 levels in these areas (Fig. 3b).

186 The predicted average ground level concentrations of PM₁₀ dust using the
187 improved dust emissions are shown in Fig 3c. Predicted dust concentrations increased
188 especially in the United Kingdom, Italy, France, Netherlands, Belgium and Germany
189 exceeding 4 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$. Total PM₁₀ concentrations are predicted to be high in urban areas
190 of Europe, such as Paris, Madrid, London, etc. and over the Mediterranean Sea and
191 parts of the Atlantic due to high sea salt levels (Fig. 3d).

192 The model using the default dust emissions underpredicts PM₁₀ with a fractional
193 bias equal to -0.41 and a fractional error equal to 0.57 (Table 3). This performance for
194 PM₁₀ is considered average based on the Morris et al. (2005) criteria. Using the
195 improved dust emissions, the model’s PM₁₀ performance becomes close to good as its
196 fractional bias is reduced to -0.29 and the fractional error is also reduced to 0.52 (Table
197 3). The corresponding graphs can be found in the Supplementary Information (Fig. S2).
198 Given that the change in dust emissions was mostly in urban areas we examine next the
199 model performance separately in remote, rural and urban areas.

200 *Remote areas:* The relatively low PM₁₀ concentrations in the remote stations are
201 reproduced reasonably well by PMCAMx in both simulations (Fig. S3). The fractional
202 bias of the model with the default dust emissions is -0.32 , the fractional error is 0.50
203 (Table 3) and the model performance is average to good. Using the improved dust
204 emissions, the fractional bias of the model is reduced to -0.24 and the fractional error
205 is also reduced to 0.48 (Table 3) with the PMCAMx PM₁₀ performance becoming good.

206 Dust represents 14% of the PM₁₀ in these stations according to PMCAMx using the
207 improved dust emissions.

208 *Rural areas:* Using the improved dust emissions, the model performance
209 improved to almost good from average (Fig. S3), since the fractional bias of the model
210 decreased from -0.34 to -0.25 and the fractional error from 0.55 to 0.51 compared to
211 the simulation with the default emissions (Table 3). In these areas, dust is predicted to
212 represent on average 15% of PM₁₀ during the simulated period.

213 *Urban areas:* The model performance improved dramatically from problematic
214 to average in urban sites with the use of the improved dust emissions (Fig. S3). The
215 PM₁₀ fractional bias was reduced from -0.69 to -0.44 and the fractional error from 0.72
216 to 0.59. This supports our hypothesis that urban dust emissions are seriously
217 underestimated in the default inventory and that our estimates in the improved
218 inventory have at least the correct order of magnitude. In these stations, dust accounts
219 for about 30% of total PM₁₀ according to PMCAMx.

220 We also examined if the improved emissions are applicable to different areas of
221 Europe given their different climate. To test this the PMCAMx predictions were
222 evaluated separately for sites in northern and southern Europe.

223 *Northern Europe:* Using the improved dust emission inventory, the fractional
224 bias of the model PM₁₀ predictions decreased from -0.32 to -0.19 and the fractional
225 error from 0.53 to 0.49 (Table 3). The performance of PMCAMx for PM₁₀ improved
226 from average to good (Fig. S4). This suggests that the increased emissions probably
227 apply to northern Europe too.

228 *Southern Europe:* The fractional bias of PM₁₀ decreased from -0.56 to -0.45
229 and the fractional error from 0.63 to 0.57 when the improved dust emissions were used
230 instead of the default ones (Table 3). Despite the improvement the model performance
231 remained average in this region (Fig. S4).

232

233 **4.1 Effect of PM water**

234 The gravimetric PM₁₀ measurements are performed at close to 50% relative
235 humidity (RH), so some of the measured PM₁₀ is water. This introduces a positive
236 measurement bias and could be responsible for part of the model underprediction of
237 PM₁₀ (Tsyro, 2005). The evaluation of the model was repeated, this time after
238 estimating the PM₁₀ water content at 50% and 60% RH using the ISORROPIA

239 thermodynamic model (Nenes et al., 1998) offline, and adding this water to the
240 PMCAMx predictions of PM₁₀.

241 Assuming that the RH during the measurements is 50% the mean PM₁₀ water
242 content concentration is 0.63 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ in the aerosol samples from the 43 sites in Europe.
243 For the improved dust emissions, the PMCAMx PM₁₀ fractional bias decreased from
244 -0.29 to -0.25 and the fractional error from 0.52 to 0.51. For 60% RH, the mean PM₁₀
245 water content concentration increased by a factor of five to 3.3 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$. As a result, the
246 fractional bias of the model decreased to -0.10 and the fractional error slightly
247 decreased to 0.48. For both RH cases the model performance is considered good. The
248 above results underline the importance of the measurement RH in model evaluation for
249 PM₁₀ especially if values above 50% are used.

250

251 **5. Effects of dust on other PM components**

252 The predicted average concentrations of PM₁ nitrate, sulfate, ammonium,
253 chloride, and sodium over May 2008 using the improved dust emissions are shown in
254 Fig. 4. The highest predicted nitrate concentrations are over the Netherlands, Belgium
255 and Northern France (over 4 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$). Lower concentrations are predicted over the rest
256 of Europe. The highest sulfate concentrations are over the Mediterranean and
257 neighboring countries such as Italy and Greece (over 4 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$). Ammonium is enhanced
258 significantly in the areas with high nitrate levels (up to 2 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) and it exists mainly as
259 ammonium nitrate and ammonium sulfate. Fine chloride and sodium concentrations are
260 less than 0.5 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ in most of Europe with higher levels over water.

261 The predicted average concentrations of coarse (PM₁₋₁₀) nitrate, sulfate,
262 ammonium, sodium, chloride, calcium, potassium, and magnesium are shown in Fig.
263 5. The spatial distribution of calcium, potassium, and magnesium is similar to that of
264 dust due to their common origin. Potassium, and magnesium average concentrations
265 are generally lower (up to 0.3 and 0.1 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ respectively) than calcium (up to 0.5 μg
266 m^{-3}).

267 To quantify the effects of mineral dust components (Na^+ , Ca^{2+} , K^+ , Mg^{2+}) on
268 the rest of the inorganic aerosol components, we performed an additional simulation
269 turning off the dust aerosol chemistry, assuming that all of the dust is inert. The
270 predicted average concentration changes of fine and coarse sulfate, nitrate, and
271 ammonium due to the interactions of the dust components with sulfate, nitrate, and
272 ammonium are shown in Fig. 6. Nitrate PM₁ decreases due to dust on average by 20%

273 over the modeling domain. More specifically, nitrate decreases by approximately $1 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$
274 m^{-3} in the Netherlands and Belgium, by $0.5 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ in northern France and parts of the
275 United Kingdom, while in the rest of Europe smaller decreases are predicted. Fine
276 ammonium decreases on average by 9% over the modeling domain. It decreases by 0.4
277 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ ($\sim 16\%$) in the same areas as nitrate does, and less than $0.1 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ (less than
278 10%) in the rest of Europe. Sulfate PM_1 decreases slightly over the modeling domain
279 (7.5% on average).

280 Coarse (PM_{1-10}) nitrate ground level concentrations increased on average 10%
281 over the modeling domain due to dust. More specific, nitrate increased by
282 approximately $1.2 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ in the Netherlands and Belgium and $1 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ in Paris. In the
283 rest of the modeling domain smaller increases are predicted (less than $0.6 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$).
284 Coarse sulfate concentrations increased and the average change is 6%. Coarse
285 ammonium increased on average 16%, mainly in marine areas.

286 Accounting for dust aerosol chemistry in our simulations leads to decreases of
287 the concentrations of nitrate, ammonium and sulfate in the fine particles and increases
288 in the same concentrations in the coarse particles. This has a significant indirect effect
289 on both the fine PM concentrations but also on the overall particle size distribution.

290

291 **6. Sensitivity to dust composition**

292 A sensitivity test was performed, in which the mass fractions of Ca^{2+} , K^+ , Mg^{2+} ,
293 Na^+ in the emitted dust were increased by a factor of two. Calcium, potassium, and
294 magnesium average concentrations almost doubled compared with the base case
295 simulation.

296 Fine nitrate decreased on average by $0.4 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ in Belgium and Netherlands,
297 while in the rest of Europe smaller decreases up to $0.3 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ are predicted (Fig. 7a).
298 Fine sulfate, slightly decreased on average less than $0.01 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ over Europe (Fig 7c),
299 while fine ammonium decreased on average by $0.3 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ in the same areas as nitrate
300 does (Fig 7e). Coarse nitrate average concentrations increased on average by $0.7 \mu\text{g}$
301 m^{-3} in Belgium and Netherlands, while in the rest of Europe smaller increases up to 0.5
302 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ are predicted after increasing the Ca^{2+} , K^+ , Mg^{2+} , and Na^+ mass fraction in the
303 emitted dust (Fig. 7b). Coarse sulfate and ammonium slightly increased (Figs 7d, f).
304 Nitrate concentrations were affected the most by the dust composition. Fine nitrate
305 decreased on average 6% over the modeling domain, while coarse nitrate increased on
306 average 7%.

307 **7. Conclusions**

308 Two dust emissions inventories (one with low and an improved one with high
309 dust emissions from road resuspension) are used as inputs to PMCAMx for the
310 simulation of the PM concentration and composition over Europe during a late
311 spring/early summer period. Use of the default dust emissions leads to a significant
312 underprediction of PM₁₀ levels, with a fractional bias of approximately -40% and a
313 fractional error of 57%. When the improved dust emissions inventory is used the
314 fractional bias is reduced to -29% and the fractional error to 52%. The PMCAMx
315 performance improved both in northern and southern Europe, but also in remote, rural
316 and mainly in urban areas with the improved dust emissions.

317 Accounting for residual water in the measured PM₁₀ assuming 50% RH, the
318 fractional bias is reduced to -25% and the fractional error to 51%. Assuming a 60%
319 RH during the PM₁₀ measurements, the fractional bias and error are reduced to -10%
320 and 48% respectively, pointing out the importance of measurement RH in model
321 evaluation for PM₁₀. While the residual water could explain part of the remaining
322 negative bias of the PM₁₀ predictions of PMCAMx there is a number of other potential
323 reasons for this behavior. The urban but also the rural dust emissions may be still
324 underestimated, there are always potential biases due to the meteorological predictions
325 (e.g., mixing heights), but also errors in the predictions of the other major PM₁₀
326 components (organics, sulfates, nitrates, ammonium, etc.).

327 Average PM₁ concentrations of nitrate decreased by 20% due to dust aerosol
328 chemistry, while average fine ammonium and sulfate decreased by 9% and 7.5%
329 respectively over the modeling domain. Average PM₁₋₁₀ concentrations increased 10%,
330 6% and 16% for nitrate, sulfate, and ammonium respectively. These results are sensitive
331 not only to the absolute dust emissions but also to the dust composition and its
332 specifically its content of soluble cations like Ca²⁺, K⁺, Mg²⁺, and Na⁺.

333 This work underlines the need to revisit carefully the emissions of PM by
334 resuspension due to vehicles in Europe. Its importance appears to be seriously
335 underestimated.

336

337 **Acknowledgements**

338 This work was supported by the project FORCeS funded from the European Union's
339 Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 821205.

340

341 **References**

- 342 Amato, F., Pandolfi, M., Escrig, A., Querol, X., Alastuey, A., Pey, J., Perez, N., Hopke,
343 P.K.: Quantifying road dust resuspension in urban environment by multilinear
344 engine: a comparison with PMF2, *Atmos. Environ.*, 43, 2770-2780, 2009.
- 345 Amato, F., Pandolfi, M., Moreno, T., Furger, M., Pey, J., Alastuey, A., Bukowiecki, N.,
346 Prevot, A.S.H., Baltensperger, U., Querol, X.: Sources and variability of
347 inhalable road dust particles in three European cities, *Atmos. Environ.*, 45,
348 6777-6787, 2011.
- 349 Amato, F.: Non-Exhaust Emissions an Urban Air Quality Problem for Public Health
350 Impact and Mitigation Measures, Academic Press, 2018.
- 351 Andreae, M. O. and Merlet, P.: Emission of trace gases and aerosols from biomass
352 burning, *Global Biog. Cycles*, 15, 955–966, 2001.
- 353 Athanasopoulou, E., Tombrou, M., Russell, A.G., Karanasiou, A., Eleftheriadis, K.,
354 Dandou, A.: Implementation of road and soil dust emission parameterizations
355 in the aerosol model CAMx: applications over the greater Athens urban area
356 affected by natural sources, *J. Geophys. Res.*, 115, D17301, doi:10.1029/
357 2009JD013207, 2010.
- 358 Bessagnet, B., Menut, L., Aymoz, G., Chepfer, H., Vautard, R.: Modeling dust
359 emissions and transport within Europe: The Ukraine March 2007 event, *J.*
360 *Geophys. Res.*, 113, D15202, doi:10.1029/2007JD009541, 2008.
- 361 Capaldo, K. P., Pilinis, C., Pandis, S. N.: A computationally efficient hybrid approach
362 for dynamic gas/aerosol transfer in air quality models, *Atmos. Environ.*, 34,
363 3617–3627, 2000.
- 364 Carter, W. P. L.: Implementation of the SAPRC-99 chemical mechanism into the
365 models-3, Final Report to U.S. EPA, 2000.
- 366 Chang, H. H., Peng, R. D., Dominici, F.; Estimating the acute health effects of coarse
367 particulate matter accounting for exposure measurement error. *Biostatistics*, 12,
368 637-652, 2011.
- 369 Denier van der Gon, H. A. C., Jozwicka, M., Hendriks, E., Gondwe, M., Schaap, M.:
370 Mineral dust as a component of particulate matter. PBL report Report
371 500099003, Bilthoven, The Netherlands: Netherlands Environmental
372 Assessment Agency, 2010.
- 373 Denier van der Gon, H. A. C., Gerlofs-Nijland, M. E., Gehrig, R., Gustafsson, M.,
374 Janssen, N., Harrison, R. M.: The policy relevance of wear emissions from road

375 transport, now and in the future—an international workshop report and
376 consensus statement, *JAWMA*, 63, 136-149, 2013.

377 Environ: User's guide to the comprehensive air quality model with extensions (CAMx).
378 Version 4.02. Report prepared by ENVIRON International Corporation,
379 Novato, CA., 2003.

380 Fahey, K. M., Pandis, S. N.: Optimizing model performance: variable size resolution in
381 cloud chemistry modeling, *Atmos. Environ.*, 35, 4471–4478, 2001.

382 Fountoukis, C., Nenes, A.: ISORROPIA II: a computationally efficient thermodynamic
383 equilibrium model for K^+ - Ca^{2+} - Mg^{2+} - NH_4^+ - Na^+ - SO_4^{2-} - NO_3^- - Cl^- - H_2O aerosols,
384 *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 7, 4639–4659, 2007.

385 Fountoukis, C., Nenes, A., Sullivan, A., Weber, R., Van Reken, T., Fischer, M., Matías,
386 E., Moya, M., Farmer, D., Cohen, R. C.: Thermodynamic characterization of
387 Mexico City aerosol during MILAGRO 2006, *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 9, 2141–
388 2156, doi:10.5194/acp-9-2141-2009, 2009.

389 Fountoukis, C., Racherla, P. N., Denier van der Gon, H. A. C., Polymeneas, P.,
390 Charalampidis, P. E., Pilinis, C., Wiedensohler, A., Dall'Osto, M., O'Dowd, C.,
391 Pandis, S. N.: Evaluation of a three-dimensional chemical transport model
392 (PMCAMx) in the European domain during the EUCAARI May 2008
393 campaign, *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 11, 10331–10347, 2011.

394 Fountoukis, C., Megaritis, A. G., Skyllakou, K., Charalampidis, P. E., Pilinis, C.,
395 Denier van der Gon, H. A. C., Crippa, M., Canonaco, F., Mohr, C., Prévôt, A.
396 S. H., Allan, J. D., Poulain, L., Petäjä, T., Tiitta, P., Carbone, S., Kiendler-
397 Scharr, A., Nemitz, E., O'Dowd, C., Swietlicki, E., Pandis, S. N.: Organic
398 aerosol concentration and composition over Europe: insights from comparison
399 of regional model predictions with aerosol mass spectrometer factor analysis,
400 *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 14, 9061–9076, 2014.

401 Gaydos, T. M., Koo, B., Pandis, S. N., Chock, D. P.: Development and application of
402 an efficient moving sectional approach for the solution of the atmospheric
403 aerosol condensation/evaporation equations, *Atmos. Environ.*, 37, 3303–3316,
404 2003.

405 Hodzic, A., Bessagnet, B., Vautard, R.: A model evaluation of coarse-mode nitrate
406 heterogeneous formation on dust particles, *Atmos. Environ.*, 40, 4158–4171,
407 2006.

408 Kauhaniemi M., Kukkonen J., Härkönen J., Nikmo J., Kangas L., Omstedt G., Ketzel
409 M., Kousad A., Haakana A., Karppinen A.: Evaluation of a road dust suspension
410 model for predicting the concentrations of PM₁₀ in a street canyon, *Atmos.*
411 *Environ.*, 45, 3646-3654, 2011.

412 Karanasiou, A., Moreno, T., Amato, F., Lumbrellas, J., Narros, A., Borge, R., Tobias,
413 A., Boldo, E., Linares, C., Pey, J., Reche, C., Alastuey, A., Querol, X.: Road
414 dust contribution to PM levels- evaluation of the effectiveness of street washing
415 activities by means of positive matrix factorization, *Atmos. Environ.*, 45, 2193-
416 2201, 2011.

417 Karydis, V. A., Tsimpidi, A. P., Fountoukis, C., Nenes, A., Zavala, M., Lei, W., Molina,
418 L. T., Pandis, S. N.: Simulating the fine and coarse inorganic particulate matter
419 concentrations in a polluted megacity, *Atmos. Environ.*, 44, 608–620, 2010.

420 Karydis, V. A., Tsimpidi, A. P., Lei, W., Molina, L. T., Pandis, S. N.: Formation of
421 semivolatile inorganic aerosols in the Mexico City Metropolitan Area during
422 the MILAGRO campaign, *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 11, 13305–13323, 2011.

423 Karydis, V. A., Tsimpidi, A. P., Pozzer, A., Astitha, M., Lelieveld J.: Effects of mineral
424 dust on global atmospheric nitrate concentrations, *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 16,
425 1491–1509, 2016.

426 Kavouras, I. G., Nikolich, G., Etyemezian, V., DuBois, D.W., King, J., Shafer, D.: In
427 situ observations of soil minerals and organic matter in the early phases of
428 prescribed fires, *J. Geophys. Res.*, 117, D12313, doi:10.1029/2011JD017420,
429 2012.

430 Keet, C. A., Keller, J. P., Peng, R. D.: Long-term coarse particulate matter exposure is
431 associated with asthma among children in Medicaid. *Am. J. Resp. & Crit. Care*
432 *Med.*, 197, 737-746, 2018.

433 Klimont, Z., Cofala, J., Bertok, I., Amann, M., Heyes, C., Gyarfas, F.: Modelling
434 Particulate Emissions in Europe: A Framework to Estimate Reduction Potential
435 and Control Costs. Interim Report IR-02-076, IIASA, Laxenburg, Austria,
436 2002.

437 Koo, B. Y., Ansari, A. S., Pandis, S. N.: Integrated approaches to modeling the organic
438 and inorganic atmospheric aerosol components, *Atmos. Environ.*, 37, 4757–
439 4768, 2003.

440 Kulmala, M., et al.: General overview: European Integrated project on Aerosol Cloud
441 Climate and Air Quality interactions (EUCAARI) – integrating aerosol research
442 from nano to global scales, *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 11, 13061–13143, 2011.

443 Kupiainen, K., Klimont, Z.: Primary Emissions of Submicron and Carbonaceous
444 Particles in Europe and the Potential for their Control, IIASA IR 04-079, IIASA,
445 Laxenburg, Austria, 2004.

446 Kupiainen, K., Pirjola, L.: Vehicle non-exhaust emissions from the tyre-road interface:
447 Effect of stud properties, traction sanding and resuspension. *Atmos. Environ.*,
448 45, 4141-4146, 2011.

449 Lane, T. E., Donahue, N. M., Pandis, S. N.: Simulating secondary organic aerosol
450 formation using the volatility basis-set approach in a chemical transport model,
451 *Atmos. Environ.*, 42, 7439–7451, 2008.

452 Laskin, A., Wietsma, T. W., Krueger, B. J., Grassian, V. H.: Heterogeneous chemistry
453 of individual mineral dust particles with nitric acid: A combined CCSEM/EDX,
454 ESEM, and ICP-MS study, *J. Geophys. Res.*, 110, D10208,
455 doi:10.1029/2004JD005206, 2005.

456 Laurent, B., Marticorena, B., Bergametti, G., Léon, J. F., Mahowald, N. M.: Modeling
457 mineral dust emissions from the Sahara desert using new surface properties and
458 soil database, *J. Geophys. Res.*, 113, D14, doi:10.1029/2007JD009484, 2008.

459 Meng, Z. Y., Seinfeld, J. H.: Time scales to achieve atmospheric gas-aerosol
460 equilibrium for volatile species, *Atmos. Environ.*, 30, 2889–2900, 1996.

461 Morris, R. E., McNally, D. E., Tesche, T. W., Tonnesen, G., Boylan, J. W., Brewer P.:
462 Preliminary evaluation of the Community Multiscale Air Quality Model for
463 2002 over the southeastern United States, *JAWMA*, 55, 1694–1708, 2005.

464 Moya, M., Pandis, S. N., Jacobson, M. Z.: Is the size distribution of urban aerosols
465 determined by thermodynamic equilibrium? An application to Southern
466 California, *Atmos. Environ.*, 36, 2349–2365, 2002.

467 Murphy, B. N., Pandis, S. N.: Simulating the formation of semivolatile primary and
468 secondary organic aerosol in a regional chemical transport model, *Environ. Sci.*
469 *Technol.*, 43, 4722–4728, 2009.

470 Neisi, A., Vosoughi, M., Idani, E., Goudarzi, G., Takdastan, A., Babaei, A. A., Ahmadi
471 Ankali K., Hazrati, S., Haddadzadeh Shoshtari M., Mirr, I., Maleki, H.:
472 Comparison of normal and dusty day impacts on fractional exhaled nitric oxide

473 and lung function in healthy children in Ahvaz, Iran, *Environ. Sci. Pollut. Res.*,
474 24, 12360–12371, 2017.

475 Nenes, A., Pandis, S. N., Pilinis, C.: ISORROPIA: A new thermodynamic equilibrium
476 model for multiphase multicomponent inorganic aerosols, *Aquat. Geochem.*, 4,
477 123–152, 1998.

478 Pant P, Harrison RM.: Estimation of the contribution of road traffic emissions to
479 particulate matter concentrations from field measurements: a review, *Atmos.*
480 *Environ.*, 78–97, 2013.

481 Patra, A., Colvile, R., Arnold, S., Bowen, E., Shallcross, D., Martin, D.: On street
482 observations of particulate matter movement and dispersion due to traffic on an
483 urban road. *Atmos. Environ.*, 42, 3911-3926, 2008.

484 Pilinis, C., Capaldo, K. P., Nenes, A., Pandis, S. N.: MADM – A new multicomponent
485 aerosol dynamics model, *Aerosol Sci. Technol.*, 32, 482–502, 2000.

486 Querol, X., Alastuey, A., Ruiz, C.R., Artinano, B., Hansson, H.C., Harrison, R.M.,
487 Buringh, E., ten Brink, H.M., Lutz, M., Bruckmann, P., Straehl, P., Schneider,
488 J.: Speciation and origin of PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} in selected European cities, *Atmos.*
489 *Environ.* 38, 6547–6555, 2004.

490 Rzeszutek, M., Bogacki, M., Bzdziuch, P., Szulecka, A.: Improvement assessment of
491 the OSPM model performance by considering the secondary road dust
492 emissions, *Transportation Research Part D: Transport and Environment*, 68,
493 137-149, 2019.

494 Silva, P. J., Carlin, R. A., Prather, K. A.: Single particle analysis of suspended soil dust
495 from Southern California, *Atmos. Environ.*, 34, 1811–1820, 2000.

496 Skamarock, W. C., Klemp, J. B., Dudhia, J., Gill, D. O., Barker, D. M., Duda, M. G.,
497 Huang, X., Wang, W., Powers, J. G.: A Description of the Advanced Research
498 WRF Version 3, NCAR Technical Note, available at: [www2.mmm.ucar.edu/
499 wrf/users/docs/arw_v3.pdf](http://www2.mmm.ucar.edu/wrf/users/docs/arw_v3.pdf), 2008.

500 Sofiev, M., Vankevich, R., Lotjonen, M., Prank, M., Petukhov, V., Ermakova, T.,
501 Koskinen, J., Kukkonen, J.: An operational system for the assimilation of the
502 satellite information on wildland fires for the needs of air quality modelling and
503 forecasting, *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 9, 6833–6847, 2009.

504 Sposito, G.: *The Chemistry of Soils*, Oxford University Press, 1989.

505 Ten Brink, H. M., Kruisz, C., Kos, G. P. A., Berner, A.: Composition/size of the light-
506 scattering aerosol in the Netherlands, *Atmos. Environ.*, 31, 3955–3962, 1997.

507 Terzi, E., Argyropoulos, G., Bougatioti, A., Mihalopoulos, N., Nikolaou, K., Samara,
508 C.: Chemical composition and mass closure of ambient PM₁₀ at urban sites,
509 Atmos. Environ., 44, 2231-2239, 2010.

510 Trippetta, S., Sabia, S., Caggiano R.: Fine aerosol particles (PM₁): natural and
511 anthropogenic contributions and health risk assessment, Air Quality, Atmos. &
512 Health, 9, 621-629, 2016.

513 Trump, E. R., Fountoukis, C., Donahue, N. M., Pandis, S. N.: Improvement of
514 simulation of fine inorganic PM levels through better descriptions of coarse
515 particle chemistry, Atmos. Environ., 102, 274–281, 2015.

516 Tsyro, S. G.: To what extent can aerosol water explain the discrepancy between model
517 calculated and gravimetric PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5}, Atmos. Chem. Phys., 5, 515-532,
518 2005.

519 Viana, M., Maenhaut, W., Chi, X., Querol, X., Alastuey, A.: Comparative chemical
520 mass closure of fine and coarse aerosols at two sites in South and West Europe:
521 implication for EEU air pollution policies, Atmos. Environ., 41, 315–326, 2007.

522 Visschedijk, A., Zandveld, P., Denier van der Gon, H.: A high resolution gridded
523 European emission database for the EU integrated project GEMS, TNO Report
524 2007 A-R0233/B, TNO Built Environment and Geosciences, 2007.

525 Wagner, R., Jähn, M., Schepanski, K.: Wildfires as a source of airborne mineral dust –
526 revisiting a conceptual model using large-eddy simulation (LES), Atmos.
527 Chem. Phys., 18, 11863-11884, 2018.

528 Wang, K., Zhang, Y., Nenes, A., Fountoukis, C.: Implementation of dust emission and
529 chemistry into the Community Multiscale Air Quality modeling system and
530 initial application to an Asian dust storm episode, Atmos. Chem. Phys., 12,
531 10209–10237, 2012.

532 Winiwarter, W., Kuhlbusch, T. A. J., Viana, M., Hittenberger, R.: Quality consider-
533 ations of European PM emission inventories, Atmos. Environ., 43, 3819-3828,
534 2009.

535 Yin, J., Harrison, M. R.: Pragmatic mass closure study for PM_{1.0}, PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ at
536 roadside, urban background and rural sites, Atmos. Environ., 42, 980-988, 2008.

537

538

539

Table 1: Domain PM₁₀ dust emissions in the inventories used in this study

PM ₁₀ dust emissions (tons d ⁻¹)		
Source type	Low dust emissions	High dust emissions
Road transport	1509	15090
Agriculture	3185	3517
Wildfires	493	493
Total	5187	19100

540

541

542

Table 2: Total emissions of trace elements in the inventories used in this study

PM ₁₀ emissions (tons d ⁻¹)		
Dust components	Low dust emissions	High dust emissions
Na ⁺	37702	37932
Ca ²⁺	125	458
K ⁺	78	287
Mg ²⁺	47	172

543

544

545

Table 3: The evaluation of PMCAMx against daily average PM₁₀ measurements

Area	Number of measurements	Low dust emissions		High dust emissions	
		Fractional bias	Fractional error	Fractional bias	Fractional error
All sites	1136	-0.41	0.57	-0.29	0.52
Remote sites	364	-0.32	0.50	-0.24	0.48
Rural sites	505	-0.34	0.55	-0.25	0.51
Urban sites	267	-0.67	0.72	-0.44	0.59
Northern Europe	694	-0.32	0.53	-0.19	0.49
Southern Europe	442	-0.56	0.63	-0.45	0.57

546

547

548

549

550

551 **Figure 1:** The modeling domain and the location of the PM₁₀ monitoring sites used for
 552 the model evaluation (red dots).

553

554

555

556

557

558 **Figure 2:** Spatial distribution of PM₁₀ dust emissions in the high dust emission
 559 inventory for the period of 1-29 May 2008 (a) wildfires, (b) road transport, (c)
 560 agricultural and, (d) total.

561

562

563

564 **Figure 3:** Predicted average ground level concentrations of (a) PM₁₀ dust, (b) total
 565 PM₁₀ (in µg m⁻³) with the default emission inventory and (c) PM₁₀ dust, (d) total PM₁₀
 566 (in µg m⁻³) with the improved emission inventory during May 2008.
 567

568

569

570

571

572

573

574

575

576

577

578

579

580

581

582

583

584 **Figure 4:** Predicted PMCAMx average ground level concentrations of PM₁ (a) nitrate,
585 (b) sulfate, (c) ammonium, (d) chloride, and (e) sodium (in $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) during May 2008.

586

587

588

589

590 **Figure 5:** Predicted PMCAMx average ground level concentrations of PM₁₋₁₀ (a)
591 nitrate, (b) sulfate, (c) ammonium, (d) sodium, (e) chloride, (f) calcium, (g) potassium,
592 and (h) magnesium (in $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) during May 2008.

593

594

595

596

597 **Figure 6:** Concentrations change (in $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) of PM_{1-10} and PM_{1-10} (a), (b) nitrate, (c), (d)
 598 sulfate, and (e), (f) ammonium due to dust aerosol chemistry during May 2008. A
 599 positive change corresponds to an increase. A negative change corresponds to a
 600 decrease.

601

602

603

604

605

606

607 **Figure 7:** Concentrations change (in $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) of PM₁ and PM₁₋₁₀ (a), (b) nitrate, (c), (d)
608 sulfate, and (e), (f) ammonium during May 2008 after increasing emissions of trace
609 elements by a factor of two. A positive change corresponds to an increase. A negative
610 change corresponds to a decrease.

611